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Producing knowledge about Water.

Theoretical and methodological controversies, flows, meanders, rigidities, and the pursuit of “full transdisciplinarity”

Vol. 9, N° 3

(in English, Portuguese, and Spanish)

Newcastle upon Tyne, UK

September 2022

[Cover picture:](#)

Flood Valley, Middle Parana River Basin, between the provinces of Santa Fe and Entre Rios, Argentina, near Sauce Viejo Airport, Province of Santa Fe. Aerial View (1996).
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WATERLAT-GOBACIT NETWORK WORKING PAPERS

Vol. 9, N° 3

Thematic Area Series

Thematic Area 1 - X-disciplinarity in Research and Action

Producing knowledge about Water. Theoretical and methodological controversies, flows, meanders, rigidities, and the pursuit of “full transdisciplinarity”

Jose Esteban Castro (Ed.)
Newcastle upon Tyne, UK,
September 2022

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Cuadernos de Trabajo de la Red WATERLAT-GOBACIT

Vol. 9, N° 3

Serie Áreas Temáticas

Área Temática 1 - La X-disciplinariedad

en la Investigación y la Acción

Produciendo conocimiento sobre el agua. Controversias teóricas y metodológicas, flujos, meandros, rigideces, y la búsqueda de la "transdisciplinariedad plena"

José Esteban Castro (Ed.)

Newcastle upon Tyne, Reino Unido, septiembre de 2022

Thematic Area Series

TA1 - X-disciplinarity in Research and Action

Title: Producing knowledge about Water. Theoretical and methodological controversies, flows, meanders, rigidities, and the pursuit of "full transdisciplinarity"

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Serie Áreas Temáticas

AT1- La X-disciplinarietà en la Investigaci3n y la Acci3n

Título: Produciendo conocimiento sobre el agua. Controversias te3ricas y metodol3gicas, flujos, meandros, rigideces, y la b3squeda de la "transdisciplinarietà plena"

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Presentation of the Thematic Area and the issue

This issue of the WATERLAT-GOBACIT Network's Working Papers was organized by members of the Network's [Thematic Area 1, TAI – X-disciplinarity in Research and Action](#). TAI's membership includes academics, students, practitioners, representatives of social movements and civil society organizations, among others. This TA has a crosscutting function with interlinkages with the other [Thematic Areas](#), of the Network, as it focuses on theoretical and methodological aspects concerning the challenges and opportunities facing our endeavours to produce knowledge about water from inter- and transdisciplinary perspectives.

This particular issue offers significant contributions that are relevant to all TA's but some articles also address specific empirical examples that are connected with topics covered by [TA2 – Water and Megaprojects](#), [TA3–, Urban Water Cycle and Essential Public Services](#), [TA6–Hydrosocial Basins, Territories, and Spaces](#), [TA7– Art, Communication, Culture, and Education](#), and [TA8– Water-related Disasters](#).

Clarification

The production of this issue was severely affected by the impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic and other incidents, which is reflected in some inconsistencies in the chronological information of the articles (dates of reception and acceptance, dates of publication of references etc.). We kept the original chronological sequence of the planned publication process giving priority to the sequence of volumes and issues.

The issue features five articles, three in Spanish and the remaining two in English and Portuguese, respectively.

Article 1, by Enrique Luengo González, addresses the challenges and obstacles facing scientific institutions, particularly universities, to generate the conditions required for developing, producing, and circulating knowledge that, beyond rhetorical arguments and formal statements, actually embraces inter-and transdisciplinary approaches. Among other issues, the author discusses the lack of institutional and financial resources required for the promotion and strengthening of these approaches that seek to transcend monodisciplinary enclosures. The article explores the difficulties facing universities to organize and sustain over time research teams dedicated to the development of collective forms of knowledge informed by these approaches and oriented at solving complex problems, involving a wide range of actors beyond the academic sphere. Some of the obstacles identified are the lack of resources to support the processes of mediation and negotiation to generate adequate conditions for the production and dissemination of this type of knowledge, which is needed to provide collective solutions to complex problems, including proposals for practical action. The author argues that there is an urgent need to strengthen the capacities of universities

to develop more situated, multidimensional, and complex approaches, and reorganize their teaching and research structures to improve their ability to contribute towards the development of more hopeful futures for human communities, particularly for the more vulnerable sectors. The final comments highlight some promising examples suggesting that inter-and transdisciplinary approaches have a fundamental role to play in the contributions that universities can make in providing support for solving the highly complex problems facing humankind in this historical stage.

In Article 2, Norma Georgina Gutierrez Serrano discusses the design and implementation of transdisciplinary research methods in the context of networks and groups of researchers in Mexico. The author grounds the arguments in her experience working closely with these research networks and groups which included following up, and, occasionally participating in their activities. The article gives attention to the diversity of forms and dynamics of the transdisciplinarity in research activities practiced by these actors, and draws lessons about the interrelations that have allowed these networks and groups to succeed in establishing the ground for transdisciplinary research and also discusses how their practices also nurture the emergence of new interrelations, thus contributing to the reproduction and expansion of transdisciplinary approaches even in environments that not necessarily give priority or fully support these initiatives. The author emphasises that a key principle in the creation and development of transdisciplinary research activities is “thinking and acting with care”, whereby interrelations between researchers and other actors are characterized by the presence of affective forms of human relations. In her view, transdisciplinary research is a “form of producing commons”.

Article 3, by Norma Valencio, addresses the contradictions and obstacles facing research initiatives that seek to “trespass” monodisciplinary enclosures often fiercely defended by institutional barriers, material interests and other hurdles. The author draws her reflections from experiences characterizing the production of scientific knowledge in the post-Dictatorship context of Brazil since the 1980s. She argues that during this period, scientific institutions increasingly faced the demands of social movements and other social actors affected by a wide array of socio-environmental crises and conflicts. The article examines some research initiatives that provide a model of commitment towards supporting grassroots struggles against socio-environmental injustice and inequality by developing inter-and transdisciplinary approaches and practices. Although the pioneering examples discussed are a source of encouragement, the author highlights the fact that some of the more difficult challenges and obstacles faced by these initiatives come from entrenched traditions of “disciplinary purism” and the institutional organization of the scientific system itself.

Article 4, was co-authored by Gisela Ariana Rausch, Rosa Paola Aviña Escot, Lorena Bottaro, Ana Nuñez, Franco Salvadores, Marian Sola Alvarez, and Laura Priscila Tercero Cruz. The paper is a product of a Research Workshop focused on the propositions put forward by Christian Laval and Pierre Dardot on the concept of “common”. The workshop included a Dialogue with Pierre Dardot that took place in one of the sessions. The authors discuss the implications and applicability of Laval and Dardot’s understanding of “the common” for inter-and transdisciplinary research initiatives focused on social grievances and conflicts connected with water-related environmental injustices and

inequalities in Latin America. The discussion presented draws from research carried out by the authors in Argentina, Guatemala, and Mexico. The article argues that Laval and Dardot's conceptualization of the "common" proposes a resignification of this concept and an invitation to wider disciplinary diversity in addressing the topic, which is required to develop more adequate conceptual frameworks to account for the growing complexity of socio-environmental processes.

In Article 5, Luciano Villalba and Bianca Vienni-Baptista present an assesment of the implementation of a water-related transdisciplinary research and intervention project involving university researchers, public institutions and civil society actors in the City of Tandil, Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina. The authors' analysis is informed by the heuristic Transdisciplinary Framework developed under the leadership of Vienni-Baptista. The article presents details of this methodological framework for transdisciplinary research and shows how it provides a useful tool for the design, implementation, and evaluation of inter-and transdisciplinary projects. The paper places emphasis on the complexities of processes of knowledge production oriented by inter-and transdisciplinary approaches and casts light on the significance of learning from unsuscessful activities, which often provide key information for tuning and improving the design and implementation of research projects. In the particular case examined by the authors, factors like the wider political context, the level of commitment from key participants, failures of communication between different hierarchic levels of the project's organizational structure, and the obstacles faced to achieve a meaningful involvement of citizens and community representatives, particularly women, were identified as important reasons for the eventual weakening and stagnation of the project.

We are delighted to present this issue, and wish you a pleasant and fruitful experience.

Jose Esteban Castro

Editor

Newcastle upon Tyne, September 2022

Presentación del Área Temática y del número

Este número de los Cuadernos de Trabajo de la Red WATERLAT-GOBACIT fue organizado por miembros del [Área Temática 1, AT-1 La X-disciplinariedad en la Investigación y la Acción](#). Los miembros del AT1 incluyen académicos, estudiantes, especialistas, representantes de movimientos sociales y de organizaciones de la sociedad civil, entre otros. Esta AT tiene una función transversal y está interconectada con el resto de las [Áreas Temáticas](#) de la Red, ya que su enfoque se centra en los aspectos teóricos y metodológicos relevantes a los desafíos y oportunidades que enfrentan nuestros esfuerzos por producir conocimiento sobre el agua desde perspectivas inter y transdisciplinarias.

Este número en particular ofrece contribuciones significativas, relevantes a todas las ATs, pero algunos artículos también abordan ejemplos empíricos conectados con temas correspondientes a [AT2 – Water and Megaprojects](#), [AT3 – Ciclo Urbano del Agua y Servicios Públicos Esenciales](#), [AT6– Cuencas, Territorios y Espacios Hidrosociales](#), [AT7– Arte, Comunicación, Cultura y Educación](#) y [AT8– Desastres Relacionados con el Agua](#).

Clarificación

La producción de este número fue severamente afectada por los impactos de la Pandemia de COVID-19 y otros incidentes, lo cual se ve reflejado en algunas inconsistencias en la información cronológica de sus artículos (fechas de recepción y aceptación, fechas de publicación de referencias, etc). Hemos mantenido la secuencia cronológica del plan del proceso de publicación original, dando prioridad a la secuencia de volúmenes y números.

El número incluye cinco artículos, tres en español y los dos restantes en inglés y portugués, respectivamente.

El Artículo 1, a cargo de Enrique Luengo González, aborda los obstáculos y desafíos que enfrentan las instituciones científicas, particularmente las universidades, para generar las condiciones necesarias para desarrollar, producir y circular conocimiento que, más allá de argumentos retóricos y declaraciones formales, adopte en la práctica enfoques inter- y transdisciplinarios. Entre otros temas, el autor discute la falta de recursos institucionales y financieros necesarios para la promoción y fortalecimiento de estos enfoques que procuran trascender los encierros monodisciplinarios. El artículo explora

las dificultades que enfrentan las universidades para organizar y sustentar en el tiempo equipos de investigación dedicados al desarrollo de formas colectivas de conocimiento inspirado por estos enfoques y orientado a la resolución de problemas complejos, con el involucramiento de un amplio rango de actores más allá de la esfera académica. Entre otros obstáculos, el trabajo identifica la falta de recursos para apoyar los procesos de intermediación y negociación que permitan construir las condiciones adecuadas para la producción y disseminación de este tipo de conocimiento, que es necesario para crear soluciones colectivas a problemas complejos, incluyendo propuestas de acciones prácticas. El autor argumenta que existe una urgente necesidad de fortalecer las universidades para desarrollar enfoques más situados, multidimensionales y complejos, y reorganizar las estructuras de enseñanza e investigación para mejorar su habilidad para contribuir al desarrollo de futuros más esperanzadores para las comunidades humanas, especialmente para los sectores más vulnerables. El artículo concluye con referencias a algunos ejemplos prometedores sugiriendo que los enfoques inter- y transdisciplinarios pueden tener un papel fundamental en las contribuciones que las universidades pueden hacer para apoyar la resolución de los muy complejos problemas que enfrenta la humanidad en este período histórico.

En el Artículo 2, Norma Georgina Gutiérrez Serrano discute el diseño e implementación de métodos de investigación transdisciplinarios en el contexto de redes y grupos de investigación en México. La autora basa los argumentos en su experiencia de trabajo muy cercana con esas redes y grupos, que incluye el seguimiento y, ocasionalmente, también la participación directa en algunas de sus actividades. El artículo enfoca la atención sobre la diversidad de formas y dinámicas de las actividades de investigación transdisciplinaria desarrolladas por estos actores y extrae lecciones sobre las interrelaciones que han permitido que dichas redes y grupos tengan éxito en establecer los fundamentos para la investigación transdisciplinaria y también analiza cómo sus prácticas propician la emergencia de nuevas interrelaciones, contribuyendo a la reproducción y expansión de enfoques transdisciplinarios inclusive en ambientes en los que no necesariamente se da prioridad o apoyo suficiente a dichas iniciativas. La autora enfatiza que un principio clave en la creación y desarrollo de actividades de investigación transdisciplinaria es “pensar y actuar con cuidado”, lo que fomenta que las interrelaciones entre investigadora/es y otros actores se caractericen por la presencia de formas afectivas de relaciones humanas. En su perspectiva, la investigación transdisciplinaria es una “forma de producir “comunes”.

El Artículo 3, escrito por Norma Valencio, trata sobre las contradicciones y obstáculos que afectan a las iniciativas de investigación que se proponen “traspasar los encierros monodisciplinarios, frecuentemente defendidos con fiereza a través de barreras institucionales, intereses materiales y otros impedimentos. La autora extrae sus reflexiones de experiencias que han caracterizado la producción de conocimiento científico en Brasil, en el contexto pos-Dictadura desde la década de 1980. Ella argumenta que durante este período las instituciones científicas han estado sujetas a las demandas de movimientos sociales y otros actores afectados por un amplio rango de crisis y conflictos socio-ambientales. El artículo examina algunas iniciativas de investigación que proveen un modelo de compromiso orientado a apoyar las luchas de base contra la injusticia y la desigualdad socio-ambientales mediante el desarrollo de enfoques y prácticas inter- y transdisciplinarias. Si bien los ejemplos pioneros discutidos en el trabajo son una fuente de estímulo, la autora enfatiza que algunos de

los obstáculos y desafíos más difíciles de superar para el desarrollo de estas iniciativas provienen de las tradiciones de “purismo disciplinario” atrincheradas y de la propia organización institucional del sistema científico.

El Artículo 4 es resultado de la coautoría de Gisela Ariana Rausch, Rosa Paola Aviña Escot, Lorena Bottaro, Ana Núñez, Franco Salvadores, Marian Solá Álvarez, y Laura Priscila Tercero Cruz. El trabajo es el producto de un Taller de Investigación centrado en las proposiciones de Christian Laval y Pierre Dardot sobre el concepto de “común”. El Taller incluyó un Diálogo con Pierre Dardot, que tuvo lugar en una de las sesiones. La/os autora/es discuten las implicaciones y aplicabilidad de la propuesta sobre lo “común” de Laval y Dardot en iniciativas de investigación inter- y transdisciplinarias que estudian agravios y conflictos conectados con injusticias y desigualdades ambientales relacionadas con el agua. La discusión presentada se basa en investigaciones realizadas por la/os autora/es en Argentina, Guatemala y México. El artículo argumenta que la conceptualización de lo “común” de Laval y Dardot propone una resignificación de este concepto y una invitación a ampliar la diversidad disciplinaria en estudios sobre este tema, con el fin de desarrollar marcos conceptuales más adecuados para dar cuenta de la creciente complejidad de los procesos socio-ambientales.

En el Artículo 5, Luciano Villalba y Bianca Vienni-Baptista presentan una evaluación de la implementación de un proyecto de investigación e intervención relacionado con el agua, de carácter transdisciplinario, con la participación de investigadores universitarios, instituciones públicas y actores de la sociedad civil en la Ciudad de Tandil, Provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina. El análisis de los autores parte del Marco Transdisciplinario heurístico desarrollado bajo dirección de Vienni-Baptista. El artículo presenta detalles de este marco metodológico para investigaciones transdisciplinarias y muestra cómo este marco suministra un instrumento útil para el diseño, implementación y evaluación de proyectos inter- y transdisciplinarios. El trabajo enfatiza las complejidades de los procesos de producción de conocimiento orientados por enfoques inter- y transdisciplinarios y destaca la importancia de aprender de los resultados no exitosos, los cuales proveen información clave para poder afinar y mejorar el diseño e implementación de proyectos de investigación. En el caso particular examinado por los autores, factores como el contexto político más amplio, el nivel de compromiso de participantes clave, fallas de comunicación entre diferentes niveles de la jerarquía de la estructura organizativa del proyecto y los obstáculos encontrados para poder garantizar una inclusión significativa de la ciudadanía y de representantes de la comunidad, particularmente mujeres, fueron identificados como razones importantes que explican el debilitamiento y ulterior estancamiento del proyecto.

Presentamos este número con mucho agrado y les deseamos una lectura placentera y fructífera.

José Esteban Castro

Editor

Newcastle upon Tyne, septiembre de 2022

Artículo 5

Inter- and Transdisciplinary research in Integrated Water Resources Management: insights from a case study in Tandil, Buenos Aires, Argentina

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Abstract

While integrated water governance approaches, such as Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), are constantly promoted in the sustainability agenda, they face several challenges, especially in developing countries, where monetary resources are scarce and socioeconomic contexts are unstable. Moreover, the baseline is often a problematic but resilient configuration of a complex system, which calls for inter- and transdisciplinary (ID and TD) research. However, the adoption of these approaches for IWRM implementation is still limited, while their use to analyse IWRM past experiences is even less frequent. In this article, we use the TD heuristic framework developed by Vienni-Baptista *et al.* (2022) to study a series of IWRM workshops conducted in Tandil, Argentina. Our results show that methodological weakness can excessively extend the problem-framing phase, conditioning the process outputs. Regarding actors, our analysis suggests that the engagement of citizens is not only ethically relevant, but may be crucial to impulse the actions needed to foster IWRM.

Keywords: Integrated Water Resources Management; Transdisciplinary research; Case study; Failed experiences; Tandil.

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³ As explained in the Presentation of this issue, the chronological information of some articles is not consistent with the publication date of this issue of the Working Papers. This is the case in this particular article.

Resumen

Aunque los enfoques orientados a la gobernabilidad integrada del agua, como la Gestión Integrada de Recursos Hídricos (GIRH), son promovidos constantemente en la agenda de la sustentabilidad, estos enfoques sufren desafíos diversos, especialmente en los países en desarrollo, en los cuales los recursos económicos son escasos y los contextos socioeconómicos son inestables. Además, el punto de partida para la aplicación de estos enfoques es frecuentemente una configuración problemática, aunque resiliente, de un sistema complejo, lo cual requiere investigación de carácter inter- y transdisciplinario (ID yTD). Sin embargo, la adopción de este tipo de abordajes para la implementación de GIRH continúa siendo muy limitada, a la vez que su empleo para analizar experiencias de GIRH pasadas es aún menos frecuente. En este artículo desarrollamos el enfoque heurístico TD, desarrollado por Vienni-Baptita *et al.* (2022) para analizar una serie de talleres de trabajo de GIRH desarrollados en Tandil, Argentina. Nuestros resultados muestran que la debilidad metodológica puede prolongar excesivamente la fase de especificación del problema, condicionando los resultados del proceso. Con relación a los actores participantes, nuestro análisis sugiere que el involucramiento de la ciudadanía no es solamente significativo éticamente, sino que también puede ser crucial para impulsar las acciones necesarias para impulsar la implementación de GIRH.

Palabras clave: Gestión Integrada de Recursos Hídricos; Investigación transdisciplinaria; Estudio de caso; Experiencias fallidas; Tandil.

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⁴ Como se explica en la Presentación de este número, la información cronológica de algunos artículos no es consistente con la fecha de publicación de este número de los Cuadernos de Trabajo. Este es el caso en este artículo particular.

Introduction

Water is a key-life resource at the core of global sustainability challenges. While water demand is foreseen to grow between 20 to 30% by 2050 (United Nations, 2023), local-scale impacts of water scarcity and freshwater pollution are enlarging and accelerating worldwide (FAO, 2022). Moreover, global green water (particularly soil moisture) and blue water impacts were recently confirmed as being beyond a safe operating limit for the Earth system (Richardson *et al.*, 2023; Wang-Erlandsson *et al.*, 2022).

The closure of the sixth assessment cycle of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reaffirmed that climate change affects and will negatively impact water resource management in aspects such as water supply security, water quality, and flood hazards (IPCC, 2022). Changes in precipitation patterns and water availability can undermine the productivity of agriculture, energy, and industry, reduce water for health and sanitation, and harm freshwater ecosystems (*ib.*). In developing countries, water resource management (WRM) is particularly challenging due to their underlying vulnerabilities (IPCC, 2022), as illustrated by the water crisis suffered by Uruguay (Goyenola, 2023). In this context, water resource governance becomes a crucial aspect of sustainability (Gupta *et al.*, 2013), straining for the adoption of integrated approaches to water management (IPCC, 2022). Though sensible in the current environmental crisis, this claim is not new; it was already present in the first discussions about the human environment (UN, 1972). During the 1997 United Nations Water Conference “[t]here was general consensus that increased attention should be given to the integrated planning, development and management of water resources”, and “[t]he necessity for integrated water and land-use planning was stressed” (United Nations, 1977 : 110).

Through the 1990s, the sustainable management of water resources and wastewater became internationally recognized as a multi-scale pressing challenge with vital impacts on ecosystem health and human development. The emergence of the Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) framework, as a result of the 1992 International Conference on Water and the Environment in Dublin and the Agenda 21 process (Agarwal *et al.*, 2000), consolidated the general water governance principles that would shape the international development programs of the current century. These principles included the recognition that water is a finite and vulnerable resource and the adoption of participatory approaches (involving users, planners, and policymakers at all levels) with special attention to the role of women (*ib.*).

However, despite these advances, during the transition to and the early stages of the 21st Century, IWRM was still not explicitly present in the definition of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), even if WRM was considered an underpinning enabler of most of them (Muller & GWP, 2006). The Johannesburg Plan of Implementation, resulting from the 2002 World Summit on Sustainable Development, definitely propelled IWRM as a core component of international development plans (UN-Water, 2017). In 2008 and 2012, countries reported the first advances in IWRM implementation (UNEP, 2018). In 2015, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development included IWRM as part of the explicit objective of ensuring the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all in its Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6. SDG 6 targets the universal access to Water Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) services for all (SDG 6.1 and 6.2), the improvement of water quality through pollution control and its efficient (re)

use (SDG 6.3 and 6.4), and the implementation of IWRM at all levels (6.5), among other relevant targets and transversal demarches such as public participation. Berisha *et al.* (2022) highlight that, besides the wideness and ambition of the SDG framework, some targets and indicators are unable to grasp the complexity of the challenges they want to address. In the case of SDG 6, and particularly the objective 6.5.1, IWRM framework itself is signalled by some authors as being too “universal” or “all-encompassing”, failing to give concrete guidance for action (Azhoni *et al.*, 2018; Grison *et al.*, 2023; Gupta *et al.*, 2013; Medema *et al.*, 2008; Swatuk & Qader, 2023). Also, the four indicators defined to track this objective are reported at the country level, even if crucial decisions regarding IWRM are made at -sub-national- basins, and city levels (Grison *et al.*, 2023). In any case, IWRM is, by definition, a problem whose complexity may include, among other: 1) the involvement of several jurisdictional levels and the existence of multiple actors in each level; 2) the diversity of resource uses and of pollutions sources; 3) the discordance between geographic and administrative borders; 4) in developing countries, severe resources limitations.

Moreover, the baseline from which SDG (and IWRM) implementation starts is very often a problematic but resilient configuration of related complex systems (Markard *et al.*, 2012), evolving under uncertainties and influenced by specific contexts, constituting “wicked” or “complex” problems (Elmqvist, 2018; Grin *et al.*, 2011; Haan & Heer, 2015; Rittel & Webber, 1973). Following Pohl and Hirsch Hadorn (2007), the challenge is, therefore, not only to know what is the systems’ desired state (target knowledge), but also to understand how the systems are functioning (system knowledge), and how to transform existing practices and introduce desired ones (transformation knowledge). How to address “wicked” or persistent complex problems has been, for several decades now, the focus of investigation for different fields of knowledge. Approaches such as post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993), interdisciplinary (ID) and transdisciplinary (TD) research (Pohl *et al.*, 2010), and sustainability transitions (Loorbach *et al.*, 2017), have addressed the question of how to better design, implement, and analyse science-policy boundary-spaces of co-production of knowledge between academic and non-academic actors. Such interface between science, society and policy is considered vital to achieve the transformation of these real-world problems (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993).

In this context, pressing sustainability problems call for a transdisciplinary perspective in the sense that scientific and societal actors work together in a co-production process (Pohl *et al.*, 2017). This research approach seeks for transformative processes of knowledge co-production. Societal and scientific actors get together to jointly frame the research problem in order to cope with societal challenges. The process of integration is central in transdisciplinary settings, as different perspectives, methods, data and expectations are put together to be synthesised in an overarching understanding of the research problem (Pohl *et al.*, 2021). To achieve an integrated output, specific expertise and skills need to be harnessed (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2022). Certainly, some of these aspects, such as multi-stakeholder engagement, have been present in the IWRM discussions since the first international meetings on this topic. The 1977 Mar del Plata Water Conference, called for “[a]n integrated interdisciplinary-approach to the formulation of water policies and appropriate legislative and administrative arrangements” (United Nations, 1977: 110). Accounting for that, Medema *et al.* (2008) relate IWRM with the post-normal science notion of the extended peer community and with the notion of socially robust “Mode 2 Science”, which is one of the roots of TD research (Gibbons, 1994).

Nevertheless, the adoption of TD as a framework for implementing and improving IWRM is still limited (Krueger *et al.*, 2016; Sigel *et al.*, 2014; Scholz *et al.*, 2000), even despite that, as showed by the work of Hoffman *et al.* (2016; 2019), this relation can be fruitful, improving both the success of IWRM implementation and transdisciplinarity itself. However, some aspects of TD research are completely unexplored. For example, one of the concerns in the TD field is the reflexivity process that aids researchers and practitioners to learn from their experiences, whether these are successful or not (Pohl *et al.* 2010). Many experiences are interrupted without achieving significant outcomes and, even if it is recognized that important insights can be obtained from failures, in most cases these knowledge opportunities are lost (Klein, 2021). But lessons should and could be systematised from failed experiences, especially in Latin American countries where these initiatives take so many resources and time (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022).

In this article, we take as a case study an experience that took place in Tandil, a medium-sized city of Buenos Aires Province, in Argentina. A set of workshops were developed with the aim of co-constructing public policies in a wide range of areas, including sustainability and IWRM. We argue that analysing these experiences with the lens of inter- and transdisciplinary research contributes to better understanding key aspects of the implementation of IWRM. The article is organised as follows. First, we present the rationale, and main characteristics of the heuristic framework that guided this study. Then, we elaborate on the methods and detail the characteristics of the case study. We provide a thorough description of the context in which the case was developed, and the historical and geographical conditions that influence it. After that, we present the results of our analysis, while discussing these findings based on the three dimensions comprising the heuristic framework, highlighting the lessons learnt from this experience. We finalise with some conclusions about the significance of participatory processes in integrated water management.

Rationale. The transdisciplinary research process

There is a large body of literature analysing practices of interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity, which highlights remaining challenges and obstacles at the epistemic and institutional levels (Vienni-Baptista & Klein, 2022). ID and TD are still rarely recognized by many academic institutions as useful approaches to address societal challenges and sustainability issues (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022). Inter- and transdisciplinarity cover a heterogeneity of practices and formats (Pohl *et al.*, 2021), but still have little influence on the institutional level. While there is a large literature dedicated to reflecting on different angles of the phenomenon of ID and TD research, it has not resulted in a more substantive basis for practices in Higher Education institutions (Vienni-Baptista & Klein, 2022). Lack of integrative understanding of how ID and TD research initiatives have been developed among different geographically diverse communities prevails within and among different regions and continents (Vienni Baptista & Klein, 2022).

In an ideal-typical characterization of a research process, transdisciplinary scholars have largely elaborated on distinguishing three stages of this approach: problem framing, problem analysis, and exploration of impact (Jahn *et al.*, 2012; Lang *et al.*, 2012). In the context of sustainable development, transdisciplinary research links two processes of knowledge production and problem framing: a scientific process to produce knowledge about a particular sustainability concern, and a societal process to provide knowledge and practices to address it (Pohl *et al.*, 2021). In this paper, we follow a definition of transdisciplinarity that focuses on problem-solving, linking processes that place the emphasis on the ground or on the realm of practice (as defined by Pohl *et al.*, 2017), and those from the realm of science, which share the goal of achieving transformational changes (Alvial Palavicino *et al.*, 2023). Klein (2014) notes that underlying the core characteristics of TD research, there are growing concerns about the science-society interface and the need for innovative methods and processes for knowledge production that are relevant to societal challenges (Alvial Palavicino *et al.*, 2023). A transdisciplinary research process can be messy and complex, and its outputs can sometimes not be entirely foreseen (Pohl *et al.*, 2021). These features require going through different stages and, within each of them, identifying specific challenges and intermediate steps, something that we reflect in our case study.

Inter- and transdisciplinarity in Latin America

In Latin America, the push for more democratic knowledge production processes has given place to rethinking the impact of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research processes in the context of the region (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022). For such modes of knowledge production to be accountable in the region, we argue that practices need to be “situated” and acknowledged as “expertise”.

Situated expertise encompasses not only the situatedness of practices and processes, but also their political (and potentially transformative) dimensions in tracing power imbalances (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022: 11).

The concept of “situated knowledge” proposed by Haraway (1988) is useful for our analysis, as it highlights the relevance of knowledge derived from the location and

features of the “knowing subject” (Leyva Solano *et al.*, 2008).

In this paper, we take the heuristic framework developed by Vienni-Baptista *et al.* (2022) as a foundation to identify the challenges of fostering transdisciplinary research in the Argentinian context. The framework allows scientific and societal actors involved in research processes to identify and systematise their expertise, while recognising marginalised perspectives, interests and motivations that are usually kept silent. In the case study we analyse in this paper, the framework offered us an analytical tool to re-signify research practices by (i) determining what was left behind and needs to be taken into account in the following research phases; (ii) bringing the implicit together with the explicit, considering the tacit knowledge of integration and implementation processes (Pearce & Ejderyan, 2020); and (iii) managing the tensions of the dialogic process characterized by “knowing that”, “knowing-why” and “knowing-how” (Mitchell *et al.*, 2015) to identify power imbalances in integration and implementation processes. Following Vienni-Baptista *et al.* (2022), we used the three dimensions of analysis that characterise the multiple ways to engage in knowledge production and expertise: (i) the context in which projects are embedded, (ii) the (inter-)relations among different societal actors and (iii) the methods put into practice. These dimensions constitute the foundations for the framework we elaborate on in the next section.

Like an *agora* (Nowotny *et al.*, 2001), the first dimension, “context”, provides the arena where knowledge is produced and implemented (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993). It is a dynamic space where problems, actors and methods converge. This interaction fosters a learning scenario that facilitates the integration of multiple perspectives and contributions from different scientific and societal actors (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022). The second dimension, “actors”, implies the re-definition of the role of scientific and societal actors (Jasanoff, 2004). A horizontal and non-hierarchical process may instead lead to “hybrid knowledges”. These are defined as knowledge systems (both local and empirical) that enrich modern science by integrating significant elements of other knowledges (Vessuri, 2004). The third dimension of analysis implies the choice and adaptation of “methods” for knowledge production developed by different societal actors (Escobar, 2014). This dimension also comprises the integration and implementation of the new (co-)produced knowledge (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022). By “integration”, we understand the convergence and synthesis of different knowledges, perspectives, insights, interests, conflicts and collaborative approaches towards a problem and its potential solutions, allowing for diversity and the fostering of mutual respect and accessibility to knowledge (Pohl *et al.*, 2021).

This heuristic framework helps researchers and practitioners alike to study and systematise situated expertise (Clarke *et al.*, 2015) in integration and implementation processes, allowing to better position the lessons learnt. Each of the dimensions detailed above contain a set of questions that help researchers and practitioners to systematise lessons and rethink co-production processes. Figure N° 1 details the questions that guided the analysis of our case study together with the dimensions and categories of the heuristic framework (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022).

Figure N° 1. Heuristic framework for situating expertise in vulnerable contexts*.

*The framework entails three dimensions (context, actors and methods), their categories and three spheres (know-why, know-that; and know-how) together with their three areas of articulation: (A) integration for justification, (B) integration for understanding; and (C) integration for implementation.

Source: Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022 (reproduced with permission).

As shown in Figure N° 1, the heuristic framework implies three types of integration processes (A, B, and C) and three types of expertise (“know-that”, “know-how” and “know-why”). Due to the characteristics of the case study we systematised, we did not apply the framework in full but rather used it as a guideline for the analysis. We explain our methodological decisions in the next section.

Methods. Data collection and data analysis

The methodological approach consisted of a detailed reflexive and autoethnographic analysis of a case study (Hughes & Pennington, 2017; Stake, 1995). One of the article's authors was involved in some of the workshops under study here. The second author contributed specific expertise to the data collection and data analysis aspects of the study, acting as an outsider to the case. We developed an approach to critically reflect on the experiences entailed in the case study based on the analytical framework discussed in the previous section. Such heuristic can be applied in advance or after the transdisciplinary process is conducted. In the case we studied, this was used as an analytical framework after the workshops were conducted.

The value of the selected case lies in the following criteria (Stake, 1995): (i) the case analysed in this article was the first — and so far only case — of multi-stakeholder engagement involving Tandil's Municipality to assess complex issues related to Integrated Water Resources Management; and (ii) this was a year-long process of regular meetings with regional scientific experts and decision-makers from key agencies. Thus, it is assumed that, from the case, it is possible to access a better understanding of the role that transdisciplinarity has in water management processes and how these are enacted in sustainability processes (Eisenhardt, 1991). We applied a qualitative methodology. In the data collection phase (Charmaz, 2014), we conducted a textual narrative synthesis of academic literature (Xiao & Watson, 2019). We first revisited publications related to the topic that helped us anchoring the heuristic framework for the analysis of the case study. To analyse these documents, we developed a qualitative content-analysis approach (Charmaz, 2014). The framework presented in the previous section was used as the foundation to design an interview guideline for semi-structured interviews (Charmaz, 2014). Five semi-structured interviews were conducted with key societal actors who organised and participated in the workshops (see Interviews). Interviewees were selected on the basis of their role in relation to the topic and the workshops (see next section on Case Setting). These were also analysed following a qualitative content-analysis (*ib.*). One limitation that is worth mentioning is the relative low rate of positive answers we received from potential interviewees. Although we contacted the main participants of the workshops, some relevant societal actors were not willing to be interviewed. We balanced this constraint with the relevant insights obtained from other two main actors who were deeply involved in the process of conceiving and designing the workshops.

Eleven protocols from the workshops were also coded. Simultaneously, the author who participated in the workshops related to the case study produced self-reflexive accounts of his experience in order to problematize the lessons learnt (Hughes and Pennington, 2017). From this phase, he conducted a self-reflexive process as a transdisciplinary researcher. We had regular meetings to characterise, analyse and compare the cases and elaborate on the three pathways between discourses. This allowed us to establish a common language between the authors of this paper and understand similarities and differences among practices, meanings, beliefs and representations in the cases in an emerging process (*ib.*).

As a result of the analytical process, we refined the dimensions (Figure N° 1) to adapt them to the case study and elaborated on the guiding questions that are used as keys for each dimension. The analytical process was developed through several iterative

phases of coding and induction (Charmaz, 2014).

Case setting

Study area

Tandil is a city located at the centre-southeast of the Province of Buenos Aires, in the foothills of the Tandilia mountain system. It is the head city of Tandil County, which has a surface of 4.836 km² surface and includes other towns. In 2022, Tandil City had 140,000 inhabitants, concentrating 95 % of the County's population (INDEC, 2023; DEL, 2023).

The city is located at the confluence of two piped streamlets, Del Fuerte and San Gabriel, which drain small watercourses from the hilly areas. At their confluence the streamlets form the Langueyu Stream (Map N° 1). In its upper section, this stream primarily relies on groundwater as its main source. However, once it enters the urban area, the extraction of groundwater for Tandil's water supply services has led to a disruption in the region's hydrodynamics, causing a reversal in the relationship between groundwater and surface water, as reported by Barranquero *et al.* (2023).

Map N° 1: The Langueyu basin and Tandil City.

Source: Adapted from Barranquero *et al.* (2023: 3), with permission.

For decades, the study of the Languoyu basin and its surface and groundwater flows has been part of the research agenda of several departments of the National University of the Centre of Buenos Aires Province (UNICEN), located in Tandil, which features 10 faculties and more than 20000 students.

The Two-Century Agreement

Even if Tandil has been a regional commercial centre for local aboriginal communities at least since the 18th Century (Ferrer *et al.*, 2022), it was officially founded by the Argentinian government in 1823, as part of the strategy of internal territorial expansion in the aftermath of the country's Independence from Spain. Therefore, in 2023 the City commemorates its 200 anniversary. In this context, in 2017, Tandil Mayor's Chief of Staff promoted a "strategic alliance" between the local government and the UNICEN to lead a process named "The two-centuries agreement" (ABC, as for its Spanish acronym), a participatory initiative congregating local organisations (NGO's, professional councils, cooperatives, etc.) and all political parties represented in the Deliberative Council, which were willing to participate.

The ABC was presented as a mid- and long-term strategy, aiming at the co-construction of a sustainable and integrated process of urban development, based on a "shared vision" for the city's future (ABC, 2019). The Municipality was expected to promote political and citizen representation, while the UNICEN would contribute with knowledge generation and reproduction (*ib.*). The ABC's official objective was "to think and design, through consensus, the public policies that will be implemented in the city, with the commitment to carry them out based on institutional responsibility" (*ib.*; our translation).

As a conceptual framework, the ABC adopted the Associated Management (AM)⁵, which is a school thought originated in the 1970s, based on experiences in Argentina, Brazil and Bolivia. It explored new frontiers and relations between the State and society in the context of complex political challenges. It is sourced (Poggiese, 2009) from the concept of interdisciplinarity elaborated by Jean Piaget (1972), Orlando Fals-Borda's Action-Research approach (Fals-Borda & Rahman, 1991) and the Pedagogy of the Oppressed and Popular Education coined by Paulo Freire (Freire, 1982). This participatory model was nurtured with other contributions, such as the proposals of post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) and with other methodologies in the "Participative Planification and Associated Management Programme" (PPGA, for its Spanish acronym) of the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO, Argentina). The PPGA provided support to counter the neoliberal policies introduced in Argentina, including the Province of Buenos Aires, and the region of the case study since the 1990s. It also informed positive transformations in the social contexts affected by the

⁵ Even if there is no explicit reference to authors of this field by ABC authorities, the inclusion of textual transcriptions of Umbarila Laiton (2015) and of Poggiese and Francioni (1993) in a reference to the official ABC document (ABC, 2019) allows us to illustrate the influential contribution of this conceptual proposal in the ABC design. Since the ABC launching, however, AM became a buzzword in the Mayor's discourses and is used very often in very different contexts. For example, in 2021 the Mayor affirmed in an interview that Tandil was an example of Associated Management because "We don't do anything if we don't talk to the Chamber of Commerce or other sectors. We also have a pillar such as the Universidad del Centro" (ABC Hoy, 2021).

implementation of neoliberal reforms (Poggiese & Francioni, 1993; Umbarila Laiton, 2015). We refer here to the PPGA's main methodological features to better understand how the ABC initiative was organised and to complement the analysis of the ABC's IWRM Working Group addressed in the next section. As (Poggiese, 1993) explains, the PPGA framework is based on three pillars: interdisciplinarity, multi-sectoriality and the participation of multiple actors. It is intended to overcome the limits of traditional planning, in which a team of technical specialists (the technical sphere) designs solutions to be implemented by professional politicians (the political sphere), and of "actionable-knowledge" production through the democratisation of decision-making and social participation. One of the core objectives of the PPGA is to create participatory arenas, as formalised spaces of exchange and convergence of actors, where complex interactions occur (Poggiese, 1993). These *agoras* are spaces for decision-making with defined rules that are built through agreements and are deployed in different phases, during the design of the participatory mechanism and during the implementation of participative spaces to define intervention strategies and their management. This implementation can take the form of "Associated Management Tables" (AMT) (Poggiese, 2011), which are described as continuous planification-management arenas where the dialogue between different societal actors takes place.

In the PPGA, the construction of those spaces need, as well as the spaces themselves later, the consensus of rules and procedures for the collective creation of knowledge, agreements and commitments, specifically developed to coordinate the work of various societal actors involved in decision-making processes (political decision-makers, thematic specialists, citizens and their organisations). Besides the call to define decision and participation rules, the PPGA framework does not promote a specific methodology to organise the exchanges between different societal actors. Thus, it is at the AMT level that "situated expertise" occurs. In the case of the ABC, the general working strategy (organisational structure, *agoras* and core dynamics) was decided by the higher-level coordinators of the Driving Team (Figure N° 2). This included: the General Coordination, formed by the higher authorities of both institutions, the Municipality and the UNICEN; the Executive Coordination, integrated by two representatives, one of each institution, the Advisory Council, composed of the Cabinets members of both institutions ABC, 2019). This "Driving Team selected ten preliminary working ""axes", defined as positive features of the desired future city, those being: accessible; integrated; sustainable; of knowledge and education; healthy; innovative, enterprising, and diversified; of coexistence and diversity; of participation and citizenship; protagonist; and of history and cultures (ABC, 2019).

FigureN° 2. Hierarchical structure of the ABC.

Source: ABC (2019)

For each subject of interest (thematic areas), the coordination teams defined two positions of responsibility, one for each institution. Finally, at the lower level, each thematic area was divided in thematic working groups, each with a dedicated representative appointed by the respective thematic area coordinators (ABC, 2019). In total, there were more than 30 Associated Management Working Groups (AMWG). The ABC's organisation expected that each AMWG could make significant progress, subject to the dynamics that could be generated by its specific participants (ABC, 2019).

The public participation mechanism defined for the ABC was the invitation of civil associations such as NGOs, professional colleges, commerce and business chambers, clubs, etc. At its launching, in April 2018, 50 institutions had signed the Agreement. Other institutions joined later. The general implementation mechanism was the organisation of regular workshops led by the coordinators of different levels. The process was documented through meeting protocols and summary reports prepared to inform executive and general coordinators. Complemented by the interviews, these registers allowed us to reconstruct, in the next section, the work done by the ABC.

Results and discussion

The implementation of the ABC started in May 2018, two months after its official launching. In the "Sustainable city" thematic area, the Municipality was represented by the Environmental Office Director, while an experienced environmental researcher participated on behalf of the University. The three working groups internally selected by the ABC coordinators were: 1) Integrated Waste Management; 2) Alternative energies; 3) Natural resources quality.

Participants of invited organisations were called for the first meeting without any information about the process to be followed nor about the planned subjects to be treated in the thematic area. During the first meeting, the 20 participants were invited to share their area of interest and their vision of a sustainable city and particularly a sustainable Tandil. Participants referred to a wide variety of concepts and subjects, ranging from physicochemical quality of the natural environment to the importance of sustainability in the long term, but also including aspects such as sustainable production, social inclusion, etc. The thematic area coordinators then presented the planned working groups. A discussion about the scope (and in some cases a reframing) of each theme followed (ABC-Acta de Reunión N° 2, 2018). In the case of Integrated Waste Management, it was specified that it included household, sanitary and industrial waste. For Alternatives Energies, some participants judged the name too narrow to represent the energy issue, which also should include, according to them, the efficient use of all energy sources; the name was then changed to "Energies". In the third case, the name was also considered inadequate and "Environmental resources quality" was proposed instead. Other topics were suggested by the participants but then discarded, such as disaster risk management, while others were included later, such as Forestry.

The Integrated Water Resources Management Working Group

The decision of addressing the IWRM issue in one of the AMT's Working Groups stemmed from a process which took several meetings (meetings were scheduled every two to three weeks). In the second meeting of the thematic area, coordinators proposed to split the group in three working groups, according to the defined thematic. Participants were invited to choose one of them, related to their main interest. The instruction for them was, as a conversation trigger, to identify, in one hour, positive and negative aspects of the working group subject.

In the Environmental Resources Quality working group, participants from 5 different institutions first identified important concepts to account for, such as ecosystem, hydrological basins, biodiversity, soil, air and water, and climate change. Then they listed weaknesses and strengths of the subject in Tandil and proposed to change the name of the working group to Environmental Assets (EA). Since then, the EA Working Group organised its own agenda. In the next meeting, participants defined two main aspects to address: first, water, under the framework of IWRM, and, second, pesticides. Regarding water, university researchers shared knowledge about several existing problems, specially concerning the sewerage system: as part of their research, several years before they established that private storm water discharges were connected to

the sewerage system provoking the overloading of the sewage treatment plant which finally impacted on the Langeyu stream's quality (Banda Noriega *et al.*, 2011).

The presence in the meeting of a representative of Buenos Aires Province Hydraulic Department, an institution related to the control of piped water courses, thrilled the participants about the possibility of addressing this problem in the Working Group. However, they highlighted that the presence of other actors would be needed, such as that of the municipal Environmental Office Director and of someone from the Sanitary Infrastructure Direction (SID). Finally, all participants agreed on the need to receive, in the following meeting basic information from one of the university experts participating in the Working Group, mainly, a summary of IWRM and its baseline for implementation in Tandil. The exposition introduced the concept of IWRM as defined by Agarwal *et al.* (2000) and summarised the research led by local water experts regarding its situation in recent decades. The information presented triggered many questions involving local IWRM challenges, such as the wastewater treatment for households' discharges not connected to the sewerage network or the possible contamination of the aquifer. Also, an NGO representative introduced concerns about water quality in rural areas, especially in schools, a topic addressed mainly through university projects related to pesticides's impacts in rural areas. Participants then decided to split the work of the Working Group in two independent groups (IWRM and Pesticides), with a wrapping session at the end of the meetings (Figure N° 3).

FigureN° 3. The IWRM WorkingGroup in the ABC's structure.

Source: The authors.

For the first independent meeting, the IWRM Working Group managed to include a representative from the Municipality's Sanitary Infrastructure Direction, and ensuring the presence of the municipal Environmental Office Director. Their presence, and that of two university researchers, allowed them to address the problem of clandestine connections of storm water discharges to the sewerage system. Also, the new actors brought to the Working Group another important, related problem: the clandestine connections of wastewater discharges (from households and industries located in the urban sector) to the drainage system that empties to water courses. This reframing

and refining of the problem helped to explore possible action paths to solve these interlinked problems. Regarding the wastewater conduits connected to the rainwater drainage system, participants differentiated the situation of the Blanco streamlet (Map N°1), which was impacted mainly by the discharge of industrial effluents (Barranquero *et al.* 2023), from that of the Del Fuerte streamlet, mainly affected by domestic sewerage discharges. Participants agreed that an inspection of the pluvial network (including the piped streamlets) could help both to detect sewage discharges and the load of rubbish and other materials carried by the street runoff. Regarding rainwater connections to the sewerage system, two different situations were identified. First, in the case of single-family households, the appraisal unearthed a wicked situation. For buildings constructed between 1995 and 2008, sanitary connection blueprints were not mandated. Therefore, to identify whether there is a sewer connected to the sewerage system, a house-to-house inspection would be needed, which could require a court order to enter the houses. Also, differences may exist between approved blueprints and the actual work carried out in the buildings. Second, for new buildings, the SID personnel were working on a “sanitary safety certificate”, which could serve as a plausible solution for the problem of inadequate connections.

Importantly, participants in the workshops also agreed on the importance of public communication and awareness campaigns focused on these problems. This was considered a key aspect regarding households because the task of checking all infrastructure works at the household level was considered unviable due to budget restrictions. In the following meeting, two new actors, from two NGOs, joined the Working Group. The Environmental Office Director was absent, and there was no institutional replacement. Conversations turned around the communication and awareness plan that should include, in addition to the information regarding the environmental impact of illegal connections, advice and warnings concerning the respective location of water boreholes and household effluents treatment and discharge sites in those sectors that do not have water supply and sewerage networked systems. In this context, participants raised concerns about urban growth over the hills surrounding the city, where the provision of effluent treatment services is very limited. Also, participants insisted on the need for inspection of the underground water network. They agreed that it was a need to analyse first the network and the land use plans, and to decide on sampling sites for microbiological analysis, to identify pollution spots. They agreed to prepare a report with this information and to request to authorities the network’s inspection and the closure of pollution sources.

Finally, the Working Group members identified several institutions that should be part of this plan, such as the Hydraulic Department (present only in the first EA meeting) or the municipal Public Infrastructure Office and the Road Management Direction (in charge of the drainage network), and others that should be engaged at the time of implementation, such as the Fire Brigade, the Civil Defence, the municipal General Inspection Office and the office of Bromatology, among others. By this time, the IWRM Working Group had: 1) A defined conceptual framework, borrowed from Arawal *et al.* (2000); 2) A concrete problem to address, *i.e.*, the interlinked clandestine connections between drainage and sewerage networks; 3) A number of measures identified to improve the assessment, *i.e.*, a desk research over the network and land use plans, a microbiological analysis sampling campaign, the report preparation and the inspection of the network (including the piped streamlets); 4) The actors to be invited to participate in the process to implement these

measures; 5) Several possible solutions to the problem, *i.e.*, awareness campaigns, the sanitary safety certificate, authorities intervention to eliminate pollution sources.

The 7th meeting of the EA and the 3rd meeting of the IWRM working groups would become a turning point of the process. For the first time, all the key actors identified took part in the meetings, including three relevant municipal authorities. Also, an environmental researcher who worked on the Langeyu stream attended the meeting. Those present recapitulated several aspects of the problem, for example regarding urban growth on the hills, and possible solutions, like the sanitary safety certificate or the communication awareness plan. Linked to this, the new environmental researcher reaffirmed the relevance of communicating about the importance of thlocal streams' ecological integrity, where several rare species inhabit but are lost once the river enters the city (Cortelezzi *et al.*, 2019). A new aspect was also introduced, related to the strategies for remediation or improvement of the ecological state of the Langeyu stream. It was established that the university could provide scientific knowledge, but that also social knowledge, its acceptance, and political will would be also required to implement coordinated projects. Finally, the Working Group agreed to work on a Geographical Information System (GIS) containing the layers of information considered relevant: the storm drainage system, the location of access to the network, current urban land uses, restrictions on use, etc. For the participants, this tool could help to better decide where to take samples for the analysis of bacteriological and ecological status, allowing the identification of clandestine connections "hotspots" and the improvement of the action plan. At the end of the meeting, it was stressed that it was essential to maintain the presence of the municipal staff, who made valuable and essential contributions.

The Integrated Water Resources Management Working Group fade out

However, in the next meeting, which was the last that year, participation decreased drastically. Municipal representatives were absent. Due to the small number of participants, both sub working groups worked jointly. The conversation turned around the ABC and the challenge of sustaining projects in the long term if that depends only on the Working Group participants, as the ABC Coordinators suggested. Then, participants challenged this idea, and included their view in the meeting's Act:

[O]ur working group understands that communication and education cannot depend on a particular initiative, linked to a specific project, but must respond to a long-term political decision [...] The municipal Environmental Office must be able to meet the needs of environmental issues, which implies increasing its level in the organisation chart, its availability of human, economic and infrastructure resources, its possibilities of interaction with other municipal, provincial and national agencies, and its decision-making capacity⁶ (ABC, Acta de Reunión N° 8 Mesa Temática Bienes Ambientales, 2018).

⁶ In 2018, the Environmental Office of the city had a minimal budget and only two persons working there.

In 2019, the first meeting of the EA Working Group was held but few people responded to the call. The Sustainable City thematic area Co-ordinator explained that the focus should be placed on the construction of a summary of the work done. This would, eventually be the last meeting of the EA (and IWRM) working groups. In April 2019, the results of the first year of the ABC were presented to the community. The work of the EA Working Group was summarised in one agreement, several proposals (working in progress agreements) and ideas (incipient proposals). One of the proposals was an Integral Plan for the Management of Household Effluent, which included four main aspects and demands (Banda Noriega, 2019): a) The implementation of the “sanitary safety certificate” for single family households; b) Higher resources to those who must control multi-family projects (hotels, apartment complexes, etc.); c) The education and awareness program to show the functioning of the sewerage system and the importance and dynamics of surface and groundwater resources; d) The analysis of existing interlinked clandestine connections, as described before. These measures were intended to: 1) stop (a), limit (b) or correct (d) in future and old buildings the inadequate connections that cause the overload (and consequent by-passing) of the sewage treatment plants; and to decrease other pollution sources (c and d). It is important to note that the impacts on local biodiversity due to the Languayu stream’s degradation are widely documented by local research centres (Banda Noriega *et al.*, 2011; Barranquero *et al.*, 2023; Cortelezzi *et al.*, 2019). After the announcements, a period of expectation started, as working group coordinators waited for instructions on how to continue. However, in the following months, the ABC entered a reorganisation phase led by its executive coordinators, which lasted for the rest of the year, which resulted in a new scope and structure of the participatory mechanism (ABC Hoy 2020). For the new phase, the Agreement focused on “concrete projects” but prioritising only four themes: 1) A Mobility and Urban Integration Plan; 2) An Integral Solid Waste Management Plan; 3) the Code of Civic Coexistence; and 3) the Production and Labour Roundtable. Therefore, the work IWRM Working Group —as many others— was interrupted. Moreover, none of the initiatives that this Working Group had agreed were implemented.

Application of the heuristic framework in the case study

This section elaborates on the findings obtained from applying the heuristic framework that served as an analytical tool (Vienni-Baptista *et al.*, 2022). The section is organised under the three main dimensions of the framework, i.e.: (i) context, (ii) actors, and (iii) methods.

Context

The ABC started in 2018, in the context of a neoliberal government at the national level, which resulted in a combination of recession (-2,6 % of GDP in 2018) and high inflation that led to a deterioration of social and economic indicators (Brenta, 2021: 343). During the first months of that year, the Argentinian government failed to access new funding sources provoking a devaluation of the local currency, the “peso”, which impacted local prices (46 % increase in 2018, against 26 % in 2017; World Bank, 2023). As the Mayor of the city was part of the same political party of the national government, political tensions increased at the local level. Some months after the launching of the ABC, and only some weeks after the first meetings, in the context of a severe economic crisis, the main opposition political party quitted the Agreement, blaming an attempt to duplicate the Deliberative Council and describing the ABC as an “helpless and empty space”, after the Mayor accused them (in other context) of only asking for reports and of being delinquents (Tandil Municipality, 2018). Also, as we mentioned above, the environmental issue was not a priority for the local government. This was reflected in the municipal structure and the budget allowed to the Environmental Direction (roughly zero). Therefore, in the first meeting of the ABC Sustainable City thematic area, some participants expressed concern regarding the imbalance between the expectations of the ABC (having a sustainable city) and the municipal structure upon which the Plan or the decided actions could be built. A participant gave an example of a Municipal Solid Waste Management project, where the municipality and the university had worked together, but that, once the funds the university were exhausted, was discontinued because of a lack of municipal support and interest. Finally, another contextual factor that conditioned the Transdisciplinary process presented in the previous section was the fact that the two main subjects of the EA Working Group, that is, IWRM and Pesticides impacts, correspond to knowledge areas already developed through research projects and action research by the university actors participating in the ABC, as seen next.

Actors

a) ABC invited institutions

As any institution-based participative approach, the ABC faced limitations related to the participation of those organisations which are not formalised, such as some popular economy sectors (Grabois & Pésico, 2015), or those people which are not organised at all (Bacqué *et al.*, 2005). In the case of the IWRM Working Group, the absence of community organisations affected by the situation of the Langueyu stream is hard to understand.

When the ABC started, a neighbourhood Working Group organised in the context of struggles related to the Langeyu stream's pollution problems, with participation of university actors, had already existed for several years. Moreover, in 2016 they had formed a neighbourhood cooperative to clean and improve the conditions of the Langeyu stream and its tributaries (Barranquero *et al.* 2023). However, they did not participate in the ABC. During an interview, one of the participants related this absence to the person they contacted to invite them (a local representative of an opposition party), who never answered the invitation to participate. This may be related to the context factors we mentioned before. If we also consider that the framing of the problem took several meetings, we can relate these aspects to the low attendance recorded in the meetings (Charts N° 1-3). Indeed, more than 40 percent of the participants were present in less than 20 per cent of the meetings, while only 30 percent of participants were present in more than half of the meetings. In this sense, a representative of the Engineers Center said: "When you have so many meetings it is hard to sustain the participation, because everyone has their own activities [...] It is very difficult when meetings become too long and repetitive to sustain them over time" (Interview N° 3, 2023).

Chart N°1. Attendance percentage by participants.

Source: the authors, on the basis of meeting's minutes.

Chart N° 2. Attendance percentage by institutions.

Source. the authors, on the basis of meeting's minutes.

Chart N° 3. Number of participants in each meeting.

Source: the authors, on the basis of meeting's minutes.

However, as Chart N° 2 shows, when we analyse attendance by institution, the results are different. Only 20 percent of institutions were present less than 20 percent of the time and more than 40 percent of them were present in more than 50 percent of the meetings. While this may indicate an advantage of an institutional-based mechanism, the global result is still weak: only 10 percent of participants and 15 percent of institutions participated in more than 80 percent of the meetings.

A factor that can explain this result is the wideness of the ABC. Institutions were invited, first, to join the Agreement, and then, to join the thematic area of interest for them. Finally, they were invited to join specific Working Groups (WGs). Some of them decided that they could not participate in all the WGs (or areas) because they did not have enough people, while others tried to do it, even if this was not always possible (Interview N° 1, 2023).

b) University actors

Regarding the role of university actors, the ABC's position changed over time. At the beginning, thematic area coordinators were asked to limit the participation of university researchers, under the premise that "the university had to be as one of the other actors, not leading" (Interview N° 1, 2023). The message was "with the university, let's slow down a little bit", "the voice that had to be listened to is that of the other institutions, the other sectors" (*ib.*). And the interpretation of that message was that the university's participation should wait. Therefore, in the first meetings, people from the university were present in representation of NGOs or political party institutions. This was indeed a mechanism some researchers and university professors found to be able to participate in the discussions.

For the university coordinator of the EA thematic area, this position of the ABC's Executive Co-ordination was hard to understand: "the university has so many things to say... Why not [to participate] as another actor?". Finally, as a result of exchanges with the executive coordinators, university researchers were invited to be part of the working groups and, in the case of the IWRM Working Group, they had a principal role (see Section Results and Discussion).

c) Municipal actors

As we explained in the previous section, due to the subject of the IWRM Working Group, the participation of municipal actors —crucial to move forward in the activities planned— stopped unexpectedly. We do not know the reasons for this decision; neither did the persons we managed to interview for this article.

Methods

The absence of methodological guidelines was mentioned as a problematic point by several interviewed participants, starting by the EA thematic area Co-ordinator: "The only thing they said us regarding methodology was "associated management", which implies participation, co-construction, therefore, a general framework but not concrete tools to move forward" (Interview N° 1, 2023).

In this regard, it is important to note that the PPGA methodology (see Poggiese

2011, 1993) is not only a general framework. However, as we mentioned in the Methods Section, only some paragraphs of Poggiese's work (without indicating the reference) were included in a document shared with the thematic area coordinators. Although some evidence of the application of the PPGA can be found in the outline of the ABC general organisation, which defined an initial group, assigned clear roles, etc., several basic premises were not respected.

For example, from the point of view of the PPGA, the design of the methodology should be participative. In the Preparatory Stage, as described by Poggiese (2011), the aim is to anticipate the initial collaboration of different stakeholders as they envision and shape future stages of the unfolding process. This involves engaging in an interactive exercise aimed at foreseeing possibilities. This was not the case in the ABC, and is one of the improvement recommendations mentioned by the Sustainable Tandil thematic area Co-ordinator:

When they called me, the ABC was already organised [...] Political-institutional decisions were already made [...] the thematic area and the themes were defined [...] They called me when they realised they needed someone to coordinate the Sustainable Tandil thematic area [...] And that is one of the critics I make [...] one of the things that should be thought before was how to include those who would participate in the [thematic area] coordination at the moment of taking that decisions (Interview N° 1 (2023)).

Also, she compared the ABC work with a past successful experience where the University and the Municipality had worked together in the environmental evaluation of a planned Dangerous Waste Treatment Plant. "In that opportunity [...] who led that process was the university". Also "there was a clear objective" and "the scope of the work was concrete and we could work relatively well from a methodological point of view" (*ib.*). The lack of methodological recommendations was also signalled by the IWRM Working Group Co-ordinator, who affirmed that "nobody told us how to work nor where we should arrive" (Interview N° 2, 2023). Thus, for her, the only methodological proposition was to meet together and discuss about problems related to the Working Group's theme, trying to achieve consensus on what was important for the city. But "it was not clear what would happen with that, what would come after, and, in the case of the IWRM Working Group, nothing happened". Here we can identify two important aspects. First, the lack of expertise in research integration and implementation, already discussed in the literature (Bammer *et al.*, 2020). Second, the lack of systematisation of past experiences, even the successful ones: often researchers can recall fruitful Transdisciplinary processes, but the absence of a reflexive and learning role (Pohl *et al.* 2010) does not allow them to take advantage of those experiences.

However, the challenge that integration and implementation represented was not ignored by participants of the ABC. For example, since the first meeting of the SustainableCity Thematic Area, some participants expressed concern not only regarding the methodology to (co) produce a final joint proposal but also about the imbalance between the wideness of the objective (co-design a sustainable city) and the municipal structure upon which proposals could be implemented. Similarly, other thematic area co-ordinators argued that these aspects were to be agreed in each working working

group, according to the subject matter and its knowledge and previous works' baseline (ABC-Acta de Reunión N° 1 Eje: Tandil Sostenible, 2018). The SustainableCity Thematic Area Thematic Area Co-ordinator also signalled a more specific lack of methodological tools related to the management of the different types of knowledge. One of the main learnings for her was on how hard it is to work with actors who have very different perspectives of the same problem:

The obstacles one finds when trying to work with the voices of all actors related to one specific problem[...] Because these are different voices, voices from the knowledge (scientific, academic), from the experience of other actors with the subject [...] and it is very difficult to achieve in a same scenario, at the same moment, and to juggle, and that those who have non-academic knowledge do not feel they are less than those from the university [...] That is the biggest challenge, and methodologically we did not have any support (Interview N° 1, 2023).

Finally, if bottom-up communication was regular and pre-established, decisions taken at the higher levels of the ABC were often not communicated to the lower level (thematic area) coordinators. In fact, neither the SustainableCity Thematic Area Coordinator nor the participants of the IWRM Working Group knew why their work did not continue and we never found an answer to this question. For the representative of the Engineers Center, it was always not clear: "I thought that the analysis [phase] had ended and I was waiting for the action plan [...] I am learning from you that the work of the Working Group was interrupted [like that]" (Interview N° 3, 2023).

Knowing-that, knowing-how and knowing-why

As knowing-that "involves understanding what is required to deal with complex societal and environmental problems in an integrated way, such as knowing to look for interconnections with other problems and to explore political, economic, historical and other circumstances" (Bammer *et al.* 2020 :2), we can say this expertise was present in the IWRM Working Group. The presence of experienced people from different domains and sectors guaranteed some degree of integration in this respect, even if some sectors (community groups) were misrepresented or absent. On the contrary, the knowing-how expertise, which "involves knowing which methods or processes to use in a particular context, along with skills in those methods and processes" (*ib.*), was not mastered, as we mentioned above.

Finally, in the case of the knowing-why skills, which "refers to the aims, motivations and commitments that societal actors have and pursue in a project" (Vienni-Baptista *et al.* 2022: 4), it is important to note that actors such as the Sanitary Infrastructure Direction (SID) did not join the IWRM Working Group with a clear commitment, because the scope of the work to do was not clear. When asked about the expectations they had in participating in the IWRM Working Group, one SID representative said "we went to participate of the dialogue and to bring what we do, we expected to collaborate within our possibilities, our knowledge and experiences on the basis of what they may be requesting us" (Interview N° 3, 2023). To the question if they knew what the results were expected from the Working Group's work they could not give an answer.

The Integrated Water Resources Management Working Group as a transdisciplinary process

Considering our definition of “situated experience” (Vienni-Baptista *et al.* 2022 and see the Section Rationale), the absence of representatives from the community organisations affected by the conditions of Langueyu stream, the work of this Working Group could barely be considered a “situated experience”. Even if they would have been invited to participate in the ABC, people directly affected by the conditions of the Langueyu stream live far from the place where meetings were organised (the city center). Also, the time and duration of meetings (18 to 20:30 hs, 1:30hs duration) were constraining for all people living in neighbourhoods from the city’s periphery (Interview N° 2, 2023), as well as for people with care responsibilities, mainly women, already underrepresented in civil associations (Moreno, 2008). Moreover, even if it is counterfactual, we can think that their presence could have been crucial to avoid the IWRM Working Group’s withdrawal from the ABC. This decision was not trivial. In 2023, an investment of 10 million USD was made to double the capacity of one of the sewage treatment plants of the city, which is now working at its capacity limit. However, because of the problems that the IWRM Working Group identified and that were not solved during these years, it is possible that, in the near future, during rainy days, the treatment plant would need to be by-passed as it already happens at the time of writing this article, impacting the Langueyu stream. Also, the problem of clandestine connections of industrial effluents to the piped streamlets in the upper basin has not been addressed, and their impacts continue (Barranquero *et al.* 2023).

Concluding comments

In this article we applied the heuristic TD Framework developed by Vienni Baptista *et al.* (2022) to analyse a case study in Tandil, Buenos Aires, Argentina. Our analysis showed that progress in IWRM needs to consider the integration of knowledge and expertise beyond disciplines, with a special focus on methods, to not hinder implementation. In this sense, it is interesting to see that, in some critiques that question “what is to be integrated” in IWRM (see, for example, Biswas, 2004) knowledge integration is never mentioned. This author reviews more than thirty different meanings of “integration” in the IWRM literature, but none of these addresses the challenge and relevance of knowledge integration (*Id.*).

Also, the Tandil case study discussed in the article shows that knowledge integration and implementation are necessary but not sufficient conditions to foster IWRM. Indeed, in this particular case, it seems that IWRM would be a matter of transitioning from one situation of the city’s water system to a new, desired situation, which is affected by many contextual factors and is closely interlinked with other complex problems related to the region’s sustainability. In this context, political commitment and active involvement —at different levels— would be primarily required.

In this regard, the Tandil case study allows us to argue that the engagement of directly affected citizens is not only ethically relevant, but may be crucial to drive the actions needed to decide suitable solutions and support their implementation.

Interviews

Interview N°1. Roxana Banda Noriega, Coordinator of ABC's "Sustainable Tandil", Tandil, 24 May 2023.

Interview N° 2. Rosario Barranquero, Coordinator of the ABC's IWRM Working Group, Tandil, 2 June 2023.

Interview N° 3. Hernan Alonso, Representative of Tandil Municipality's Obras Sanitarias (Sanitary Works Department), Tandil, 28 June 2023.

Interview N° 4. Agustina Cortelezzi, Researcher, National University of the Centre of Buenos Aires Province (UNICEN), Tandil, 22 June 2023.

Interview N°5. Mariano Gerbino, member of the NGO Punto Verde, Tandil, 4 June 2023.

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